

Tool 4

Determine if citizen science fits your research

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 0 – consider), which helps you to determine if citizen science fits your research. Citizen science does not fit for all research topics. This template helps you to make a profound decision with the help of some decision-making questions.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer.

If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be. Please feel free to note these issues for our office in the box provided.

1. The importance of engagement

In citizen science, participants can be engaged in all phases of the research process. They are involved in the research as co-designers and implementers of research tasks, and not as a research object. If citizens participate as respondents in tests or interviews, or in the completion of surveys, then it is *not* called citizen science. Rather, when citizens are taking an active role in organizing or conducting these tests, interviews, surveys or focus groups, then we do call it citizen science.

To what extent can you involve citizen scientists in an active manner in your research?

- Very great extent (score 4)
- Great extent (score 3)
- Neither little, nor great (score 2)
- Little extent (score 1)
- Very little extent (score 0)

If you are not sure how you can actively involve citizen scientists, you can check the table below to identify potential research tasks. Besides these tasks, participants can also be involved in the research design and project management, such as the development of training materials, establishing a network of participants, organizing communication and support mechanisms, etc.

In which potential research tasks can citizens be involved in your research (project)?

Formulate a research question	Develop or choose a method	Collect data	Analyse data	Report & disseminate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submitting an idea • Expressing concerns • Participating in ideation sessions • Crowdsourcing challenges • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creating citizen science tools • Becoming an interviewer • Developing a measurement device • Defining a survey protocol • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photographing • Counting • Observing • Using sensors • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annotating • Transcribing • Interpreting • Calculating • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposing new directions for research • Co-authoring a publication • Speaking at a public event • Becoming a project ambassador •

Additional notes:

2. Transdisciplinary research

Citizen science is very suitable for the creation of transdisciplinary connections by constituting a research team from different scientific disciplines and different faculties. Furthermore, citizen science is often conducted with stakeholders from outside academia, such as with civil society organisations, governments, and industrial partners.

To what extent is the collaboration with stakeholders outside academia possible in your research (project)?

- Very great extent (score 4)
- Great extent (score 3)
- Neither little, nor great (score 2)
- Little extent (score 1)
- Very little extent (score 0)

Which potential stakeholders might be relevant to involve in your research (project)?

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Additional notes:

3. Promotion of scientific learning

Engaging youngsters, students and teachers in a citizen science project can help to promote scientific literacy. Pupils and students can connect with scientific knowledge and be inspired about the work of scientists. They learn how to ask scientific questions, run experiments and can draw evidence-based solutions. You can choose to design your project either for formal learning environments, e.g. as part of the school curriculum, or for informal learning environments, e.g. nature clubs, museums, etc.

Do you think your research (project) can support scientific learning, either through formal or informal learning environments?

- Very great extent (score 4)
- Great extent (score 3)
- Neutral (score 2)
- Little extent (score 1)
- Very little extent (score 0)

In which ways do you think you are able to provide training and support to citizen scientists?

- Online webinars
- Physical train-the-trainer workshops
- Email
- Online Q&A list
- Telephone
- Chat
- Step-by-step tutorials
- Videos
- I do not think I will be able to provide training and support
- Other:

Additional notes:

4. A continuum

The last decision-making factors are presented on a continuum, answers in the table to the right are leaning more easily and intuitively towards a citizen science approach.

However, this does not mean that variations cannot be developed, for instance a small-scale project with only 35 participants, focusing on one specific neighborhood. A balance must be sought between the level of engagement, the scientific objectives, and the logistical capacities of the team.

Spatial & temporal scale

If you need to collect a large volume of data along a large spatial scale over a longer period, then citizen science is highly suitable.

Complexity of the data protocol

The easier the data protocol, the better. More complex protocols are also particularly suited to citizen science projects. However, you need to be aware that only a particular profile, and most often an expert profile, will participate (e.g. naturalists, hobbyists, medical professions, etc.).

The available budget

It is a misunderstanding that citizen science is a cheap (or even cost-free) approach to collecting data. Although data can be collected in a cost-effective manner, there are several costs that you need to consider which are different from conventional science.

Spatial scale	Small	•	•	•	•	•	Large
Temporal scale	Short	•	•	•	•	•	Long
Volume of data	Small	•	•	•	•	•	Large
User-friendliness of the data protocol	Simple	•	•	•	•	•	Complex
Amount of resources	Little	•	•	•	•	•	Plenty

Additional notes: